

IMPROVING STATE BUDGET TREASURY PERFORMANCE THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

Umirov Sherzod Baxriddinovich

Toshkent davlat Iqtisodiyot universiteti 2-bosqich talabasi

umirovsherzod32@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15671372>

Annotation: The thesis is devoted to analyzing and determining the essence of the development of the treasury system and the efficiency of using budget funds through digital technologies, as well as evaluating efficiency.

Keywords: digital technologies, audit, digital government procurement, electronic platform, artificial intelligence.

Over the past few years, the level of digital development of society in Uzbekistan has significantly increased, mainly due to the following factors: the creation of a regulatory framework, the introduction of information technologies into various sectors of the economy, as well as the formation of electronic platforms that provide quick access to information resources.

With the gradual introduction of information technologies into budget processes, active digitalization is also being carried out in treasury activities, as this leads to increased economic efficiency. At the same time, the peculiarity of the digitalization of the treasury system is that it represents not a separate digital platform, but a whole system of various technologies. The most promising areas include: robotization, the Internet, 3D printing, virtual reality, blockchain, augmented reality, artificial intelligence and drones.

It is worth noting that, despite the many advantages, the widespread introduction of information technologies into treasury activities also poses certain risks: payment fraud, cyberattacks, data leakage, etc. These implemented systems require reliable protection, therefore, the treasury should expand its functions, strengthen protection, and maximize control over possible risks, that is, work diligently to protect data.

The effectiveness of digitization of the treasury system:

- ✓ reduction of payment execution times;
- ✓ reduces labor costs for downloading and processing reports by 100%;
- ✓ Reduces the labor costs of treasurers to coordinate received payment registers by 80%;
- ✓ further increases the effectiveness of budget control;
- ✓ reduce labor costs by an overall 20% to control payments;
- ✓ improves the quality of liquidity management;

- ✓ increases the efficiency of payments.

With the increasing importance of treasury, a key trend in the overall innovative development is its digitalization. The digitalization of treasury offers various opportunities, but also creates new risks that need to be managed.

A new era of treasury automation

In the future, the Treasury will be self-governing: fully autonomous processes will provide the opportunity to obtain the necessary indicators in real time, combined with the use of systematic and non-system data. This autonomous system uses a set of interacting coherent models to model the behavior of budget recipients and process large amounts of data to assess risks. Thus, the use of modern digital methods will reduce operational costs and increase the efficiency of the sector.

The experience of digitization can be transferred to treasury automation: the transformation is carried out in several stages, with new functions gradually transferred to artificial intelligence management. This process can be described using the developed elegant model of budget management automation (Figure

1), which considers the autonomous process as the highest level.

Naturally, the role of the treasurer will also change: constant human involvement in the operational activities of the budget is no longer required. Instead, employees will calibrate and test new models and methods, explaining their results - artificial intelligence will work where humans cannot replace it, simulations must be interpreted.

It is easy to imagine a wide range of applications of digital technologies in treasury - from liquidity management or asset portfolio management and optimization to ALM systems and decision making. Let's take a look at some of them.

If the budget cannot accurately forecast cash inflows, it will require large financial reserves, which will reduce efficiency. Therefore, an interesting use of new technologies for the budget may be cash flow forecasting using artificial intelligence. That is, processing large amounts of data about accounts, taxpayers, the economy, etc., to predict the future financial activity of each entity.

Potential pitfalls of automation

With digitalization in the budget system, special attention should be paid to the issue of security and data protection. At the initial stage of technology implementation (both in the choice of methodology and in data collection), it is necessary to pay attention to the use of only the data that is really necessary for analysis. In many countries, supervisory authorities are actively addressing the topic of cloud technologies. All of the factors listed above affect the potential application of new technologies. However, where technology brings significant benefits, ultimately increases efficiency or reduces risk, these obstacles are worth overcoming.

Conclusion. The Treasury is one of the driving forces in the country's digital transformation, thanks to its vast experience and technical capabilities. New innovative digital methods provide new tools for the budget system. However, the focus is not on the technology itself. Depending on the problem, you should use the method that provides the best solution - this can be a new technology or a traditional statistical method (or a combination of both). By adopting an agile approach, the Treasury can prototype new models and learn new techniques.

References:

1. Abdullayeva, h. (2021). Qishloq xo'jaligida ixtisoslashgan klasterlarni shakllantirish holati va rivojlantirish istiqbollari. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz), 7(7).
2. Qayimova, z. (2021). Buxoro viloyati qishloq xo'jaligida kooperatsiya munosabatlarining iqtisodiy tahlili. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz), 7(7).
3. Niyozova, i. (2023). Mamlakatimizda korxonalarining tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyatini rivojlantirish va boshqarish. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz), 39(39).

4. Abdulloev, a. (2023). Methodological foundations for evaluating the efficiency of agrocluster management. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz), 42(42).
5. Вакаева, м. (2022). Озиқ-овқат саноати корхоналарида замонавий бошқарув тизимини ташкил этиш йўналишлари. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz), 12(12).
6. Abdullayeva, h. (2023). Bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitida tadbirkorlikni rejalashtirishning nazariy-uslubiy asoslari. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. Uz), 37(37).

